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AI-BASED EXPERT SYSTEM DESIGN FOR OPTIMISATION OF HEAVY METAL ADSORPTION ON WASTE-DERIVED ADSORBENTS

Abstract: Heavy metal contamination in wastewater is a major global problem that requires effective, automated, and sustainable treatment systems capable of linking laboratory-scale adsorption processes to intelligent large-scale operation. This work introduces a novel Expert System (*ES*) that combines a Genetic Algorithm (*GA*), Artificial Neural Networks (*ANN*), and Monte Carlo (*MC*) analysis for the automated removal of heavy metals using adsorbents obtained from Low-Density Concrete waste. This research is significant because adsorption systems are complex to automate due to their nonlinear behaviour and sensitivity to fluctuating operating conditions. By facilitating intelligent process control and optimisation, the system overcomes the main drawback of adsorption technology, which is its lack of automation. Experimental datasets for Pb^{2+} , Co^{2+} and Mn^{2+} removal were used to train the *ANN*, which predicts removal from inputs (pH, adsorbent mass, contact time, initial concentration). *GA* then used this trained *ANN* to optimise these same factors. According to the sensitivity analysis, the most important control variables in heavy metal adsorption were heavy metal type, pH, and adsorbent mass. The *ANN* model demonstrated strong predictive performance ($R^2 = 0.908$, RMSE = 7.43 %), enabling *GA* to optimise process conditions and achieve removal efficiencies of 100 % (Pb^{2+}), 87.8 % (Co^{2+}), and 71.62 % (Mn^{2+}) under identified optimal operating parameters. Operational reliability measured by *MC* simulations showed Co^{2+} had a higher variability (*CV*: Coefficient of Variation = 5.39 %) than Mn^{2+} (*CV* = 3.29 %) and Pb^{2+} (*CV* = 2.13 %), which had minimal uncertainty. Using resources from the circular economy, the *ES* provides a framework for a digital twin of an Industry 4.0-compliant water treatment system that enables translation of lab-based procedures into practical applications.

Keywords: expert system, heavy metal adsorption, machine learning, construction and demolition waste, water treatment plant, process automation, Industry 4.0

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Abbreviations	Descriptions
<i>ANFIS</i>	Adaptive Neuro-Fuzzy Inference System
<i>ANN</i>	Artificial Neural Networks
<i>AVG</i>	Average
<i>BP</i>	Back Propagation
<i>CDF</i>	Cumulative Distribution Function
<i>CI</i>	Confidence Intervals
<i>CNN</i>	Convolutional Neural Network
<i>CT</i>	Contact Time
<i>CV</i>	Coefficient of Variation
<i>DSS</i>	Decision Support System
<i>ES</i>	Expert System
<i>GA</i>	Genetic Algorithm
<i>IC</i>	Initial Concentration
<i>IoT</i>	Internet of Things
<i>KPI</i>	Key Performance Indicators
<i>LDC</i>	Low-Density Concrete
<i>MA</i>	Mass of Adsorbent
<i>MAD</i>	Median Absolute Deviation
<i>MAE</i>	Mean Absolute Error
<i>MC</i>	Monte Carlo
<i>MI</i>	Mutual Information
<i>ML</i>	Machine Learning
<i>MSE</i>	Mean Squared Error
<i>NMI</i>	Normalised Mutual Information
<i>PCA</i>	Principal Component Analysis
<i>PDF</i>	Probability Density Function
R^2	Coefficient of Determination
<i>RF</i>	Random Forest
<i>RMSE</i>	Root Mean Square Error
<i>RP</i>	Removal Percentage
<i>RSM</i>	Response Surface Methodology
<i>SD</i>	Standard Deviation
<i>SHAP</i>	Shapley Additive Explanations
<i>SVM</i>	Support Vector Machines
<i>UN SDGs</i>	United Nations Sustainable Development Goals

Introduction

With continuous technological progress and societal development, rapid industrialisation and urban expansion have led to an increase in the release of hazardous substances, particularly heavy metals [1, 2]. The presence of these contaminants adversely affects the quality of soil and water, disrupts associated ecosystems, and poses significant risks to human health [3]. Compared with membrane, chemical, electrochemical, biological [4, 5] and photocatalytic methods, adsorption [6] remains the most cost-effective, well-established, and environmentally friendly technique for heavy metal [7-9] removal in wastewater treatment. Adsorption provides operational simplicity and high removal

efficiency even at low metal concentrations. In contrast, membrane and electrochemical systems, though offering greater automation, are generally more complex and costlier. The main limitation of adsorption techniques is their limited ability to be automated, which restricts their continuous and large-scale application. However, adsorption continues to be a practical and extensively used method for the long-term removal of heavy metals [10]. Machine Learning (*ML*) plays a crucial role in automating adsorption processes for heavy metal removal by enabling accurate prediction, optimisation, and control of operational parameters [11]. Reducing experimental effort, algorithms such as Artificial Neural Network (*ANN*) [12], Support Vector Machines (*SVM*) [13], and Random Forest (*RF*) [14] can simulate nonlinear interactions between variables, e.g., pH, adsorbent dose, and contact time. The integration of *ML* with sensors and control systems enhances real-time monitoring, facilitates adaptive decision-making, and automates adsorption-based wastewater treatment effectively.

The automation, design, and predictive modelling of adsorption processes for the removal of heavy metals have been greatly enhanced by recent developments in *ML*. In order to discover important factors that have an impact on adsorption, such as synthesis and ambient conditions, Liang et al. [15] applied *ML* to Schwertmannite, a sea urchin-like adsorbent, using an *RF* model trained on 814 data groups with 27 attributes. Leng et al. [16] optimised pyrolysis settings using only biomass composition data by using a hybrid *ML* framework that combines relationships between biomass, production, biochar, and application to predict biochar characteristics and adsorption behaviour. In order to improve soil remediation techniques, Wang et al. [17] used a variety of *ML* models, most notably XGBoost, to pinpoint important soil characteristics that affect heavy metal adsorption, such as pH, reactive oxides, and organic matter. In a similar vein, Yaseen and Alhalimi [18] combined ensemble *ML* techniques including XGBoost, LightGBM, and Adaboost to forecast the adsorption efficiency of biochar-based heavy metal, emphasising the crucial roles of pH and metal-to-biochar ratios.

The adsorption capacity of geopolymers was predicted by Han et al. [19] using an Extra Trees model, which ranked feature importance based on parameters including pH, dose, and curing time. In order to simulate biochar sorption efficiency, Hassan et al. [20] used a combination of linear, nonlinear, and deep learning methods, such as *ANN*, Convolutional Neural Network (*CNN*), and CatBoost. They also used Shapley Additive Explanations (*SHAP*) analysis for automated performance evaluation and feature interpretation. Tank et al. [21] created amine-modified mesoporous silica, applied 14 *ML* algorithms using *SHAP*-based feature dependency analysis, and created a stacking regressor to improve adsorption performance prediction.

To forecast the ion exchange resin adsorption capacity for heavy metals, Xu et al. [22] created a library of resin adsorption data by combining LightGBM modelling with attributes gained from molecular simulations. Wang et al. [23] used regression, *ML*, and deep learning models to study heavy metal adsorption onto microplastics. *RF* produced the best prediction and identified environmental factors as the main adsorption determinants. Overall, these studies show how *ML* may revolutionise adsorbent synthesis, feature selection, and system automation, enabling the development of intelligent and flexible adsorption-based decontamination systems.

The intricacy of waste-derived materials, whose heterogeneous and mixed surfaces make adsorption modelling and automation difficult [24], has not been addressed in previous studies that have applied *ML* to a variety of adsorbents. By combining

metaheuristic algorithms with *ML* models, an Expert System (*ES*) framework is created in this study to bridge this gap. This results in a novel Decision Support System (*DSS*) that allows for automated control, prediction, and intelligent optimisation of heavy metal adsorption using waste-based adsorbents.

According to the identified research gap, the present study aims to develop a comprehensive dataset from experimental adsorption processes of heavy metals using Low-Density Concrete (*LDC*) [25] as the adsorbent. An *ML* model based on the *ANN* is then constructed to predict the Adsorption Performance. Subsequently, *GA* optimisation is performed using the trained *ANN* to identify optimal operating conditions. The model's uncertainty is evaluated through Monte Carlo (*MC*) analysis, and finally, its performance is validated under a simulated water treatment plant with synthetic data in the range of experimental conditions to assess the overall efficiency of the developed *ES*.

Materials and methods

The research program starts with gathering experimental data on heavy metal adsorption utilising adsorbents produced from construction and demolition waste (*LDC*), as shown in Figure 1. Significant parameters are then found by statistical analysis. Adsorption performance is predicted by the *ML* stage (*ANN*), and then important variables are optimised by using the meta-heuristic *GA*. Model uncertainty is then assessed using *MC* analysis. Lastly, all phases are integrated for automated adsorption process prediction, optimisation, and control using the built *ES*.

Fig. 1. The research roadmap of the present study

Experimental steps and dataset preparation

This study prepares the dataset based on the study of Gheibi et al. [25]. Experimental data on the adsorption of Pb^{2+} , Co^{2+} , and Mn^{2+} ions [26] (designated as 1-3) onto *LDC* adsorbent are included in the dataset. All experiments were conducted in single-contaminant reactors. Parameters including (1) pH (2-5), (2) Mass of Adsorbent (*MA*) (1.33-10) g/L, (3) Contact Time (*CT*) (1-120) min, (4) Initial Concentration (*IC*) of heavy metals (5-200) mg/L, and (5) Removal Percentage (*RP*) as the response are the five factors that control the system. One factor at a time, experiments were planned around a baseline (pH = 5, *MA* = 6.67 g/L, *CT* = 30 min, *IC* = 10 mg/L). Additionally, to assess the adsorption rate and equilibrium behaviour, kinetic analysis was performed by adjusting *CT* at constant *IC* = 5 mg/L and *MA* = 6.67 g/L. To ascertain the effects of the parameters, each metal system was evaluated in these controlled settings. The dataset consists of 66 adsorption test results, corresponding to 66 records with five input variables and one output variable. Consistency of dataset and nonlinear adsorption behaviour provides a strong basis for statistical modelling, *ML* prediction, kinetic evaluation, and optimisation using metaheuristic and uncertainty analyses in the *ES* that will be outlined below.

Statistical analysis

The statistical analysis in this study was methodically divided into four phases. The first step was data pre-processing for four parameters (pH, *MA*, *CT*, *IC*) as standardising input variables using z-score normalisation, detecting outliers using the Median Absolute Deviation (*MAD*) [27] approach. Second, the distribution of the data was summarised by computing descriptive statistical metrics as mean, standard deviation, quartiles, skewness, and kurtosis. Third, normalised Mutual Information (*MI*) [28] analysis was used to quantify inter-variable interdependence. Lastly, Principal Component Analysis (*PCA*) [29] was used to visualise patterns and reduce dimensionality. MATLAB R2019b was used to carry out all calculations and visualisations.

ANN-GA model structure

Figure 2 demonstrates the model structure for predicting the removal percentage (*RP*) of three heavy metal ions by *ANN* and maximising the *RPs* by *GA*.

Input parameters for creating the *ANN* include Metal type, pH, *MA*, *CT*, and *IC* to predict the *RP* of Pb^{2+} , Co^{2+} , and Mn^{2+} ions. Two hidden layers, each with 10 and 12 neurons, were used with the improved Levenberg-Marquardt training algorithm, or "trainlm" [30]. To guarantee strong generalisation, the dataset was split at random into 70 % for training, 15 % for validation, and 15 % for testing. The output neuron's activation function was set to linear, and the hidden layers' to tangent-sigmoid [30]. Iterative backpropagation was used to adjust the model parameters until the Mean Squared Error (*MSE*) was less than $1 \cdot 10^{-5}$. In this model, the cost function minimises the gap between *ANN*-predicted removal and the 100 % target, allowing *GA* to adjust input factors to maximise adsorption efficiency for each metal ion.

After developing the *ANN*, a *GA* [31] was applied to maximise *RP* by optimising the input variables within their physical ranges. The trained *ANN* was used as a surrogate model during the optimisation process. *GA* had a population of 100, a crossover rate of 0.8, 50 generations, and 10 elites. In this study, mutation was implemented using the default Gaussian mutation operator, which perturbs each decision variable by adding zero-mean

normally distributed noise, with variance controlled by the scale, shrink, and initial population range parameters to preserve diversity and avoid premature convergence [32]. The integrated ANN-GA framework [33] autonomously identified optimal operating conditions, ensuring low error and high predictive accuracy across all metal systems. Stochastic uncertainty quantification over the ANN-GA optimised adsorption response is carried out *via* the MC approach [34]. MC simulations (2000 iterations per ion) randomly perturb these ideal parameters within $\pm 5\%$ to provide probabilistic response distributions once the ANN has been trained and the GA has identified the best process conditions for each metal ion (Pb^{2+} , Co^{2+} , and Mn^{2+}). In the MC analysis, metal type, defined as a categorical variable (1 = Pb^{2+} , 2 = Co^{2+} , 3 = Mn^{2+}), is fixed within each MC run and is determined separately in an outer loop, not treated as a stochastic variable. Statistical descriptors, including mean (AVG), standard deviation (SD), Coefficient of Variation (CV), and (95-99) % Confidence Intervals (CI), are produced by recalculating the predicted RP using the trained ANN model in each iteration. By combining MC-driven uncertainty propagation, GA-based deterministic optimisation, and ANN predictive mapping, the framework allows for the assessment of model robustness and sensitivity to experimental modifications *via* visual dashboards such as PDF (Probability Density Function), CDF (Cumulative Distribution Function), and box plots. Note that all the declared computations were coded and run in MATLAB 2019b.

Fig. 2. The structure of ANN-GA model in the present study, Condition: ANN: Two hidden layers (10, 12 neurons); trainlm algorithm; tansig-hidden, linear-output; $MSE < 1 \cdot 10^{-5}$; split training: 70 % - testing: 15 % - validation: 15 % and GA: Pop 100; crossover 0.8; 50 generations; 10 elites; maximised $RP \rightarrow 100\%$ *via* optimised inputs

Expert system structure

An *ES* for intelligent control of metal ion removal in an industrial water treatment plant is formed by the implemented MATLAB R2019b software. To anticipate *RP*, it incorporates a feed-forward *ANN* trained on past process data, including Metal type, pH, *MA*, *CT*, and *IC*. To attain maximum *RP* for Pb^{2+} , Co^{2+} , and Mn^{2+} , these parameters are refined by *GA* optimisation. To simulate actual water treatment plant conditions, the system creates 200 synthetic sensor-based test datasets [35], allowing for online prediction and adaptive learning.

The synthetic online sensor dataset was generated within the experimentally validated operating domain by defining the input vector $x = [m, \text{pH}, \text{MA}, \text{CT}, \text{IC}]$, where the metal type $m \in \{1, 2, 3\}$ was treated as a fixed categorical variable and continuous parameters were sampled from bounded uniform distributions $\sim U(x_{i-\min}, x_{i-\max})$. Sensor uncertainty was emulated *via* multiplicative noise $x \sim i = x_i(1 + \epsilon_i)$, with $\epsilon_i \sim U(-0.02, 0.02)$ followed by range projection. Subsequently, *MC* analysis perturbed the *ANN-GA* optimised parameters within $\pm 5\%$ over multiple realisations to quantify process-level uncertainty around the optimal operating point. The 2% simulated sensor uncertainty represents a controlled and reliable measurement regime, while the 5% *MC* perturbation encompasses broader process and operational variability; thus, the smaller sensor noise is intentionally nested within the larger *MC* uncertainty to reflect the hierarchical nature of measurement and operational uncertainties.

The *ES* assesses operational dependability and model robustness using visual dashboards (response surfaces, Key Performance Indicators: *KPIs*, and process flow) and performance indicators (Coefficient of Determination: R^2 , Root Mean Square Error: *RMSE*, and Mean Absolute Error: *MAE*). While further work concentrates on *ES* performance validation under dynamic water treatment scenarios, the structure permits interfacing with sensors for autonomous optimisation.

Results and discussion

At the first stage, the specification of the dataset and available experimental results of Pb^{2+} , Co^{2+} , and Mn^{2+} adsorption onto the surface of *LDC* is analysed. A thorough summary of the features of the input dataset, inter-variable dependencies, and their overall variance structure relative to the *RP* is given in Figure 3.

The dataset was deemed complete, since there were no missing values in any of the response parameters (removal percentage) or input parameters (Metal type, pH, *MA*, *CT*, and *IC*). This validated the data's reliability for subsequent statistical analysis and modelling. Figure 3a shows the Normalised Mutual Information (*NMI*) matrix between the input variables. The off-diagonal *NMI* values remain below 0.12, indicating that each input delivers significantly independent information and confirming weak correlations among variables. A slight correlation (≈ 0.12) is observed between *CT* and *IC* in the adsorption test results. However, the categorical variable metal type exhibits negligible mutual information with all continuous variables, confirming minimal redundancy. Moreover, as metal type is a categorical variable, its low correlation with continuous parameters is expected and does not imply a lack of influence on removal efficiency. Therefore, the inclusion of all predictors in the modelling framework is justified, and the risk of multicollinearity is substantially reduced. Boxplots, which are a valuable tool for visualising central tendency, dispersion, and the existence of high-leverage observations, are used to display the input

variable distributions in Figure 3b. The pH variable has a clear left skew (skew = -2.81 , kurtosis = 9.9 , median = 5), with a few low extreme values. The MA variable exhibits a moderately left-skewed distribution (skew = -1.18 , kurtosis = 5.84), with most values clustered around 6.67 g/L and a limited number of high-leverage observations, indicating general consistency with occasional deviations. CT displays a broad and right-skewed distribution (skew = 2.08 , kurtosis = 6.41), spanning from 10 to 120 min, with 26 high-value influential observations. IC demonstrates the most pronounced non-Gaussian behaviour, with an extreme right skew (skew = 3.33 , kurtosis = 13.63), a dominant median of 10 mg/L, and nine high-leverage observations up to 200 mg/L, reflecting irregular concentration spikes.

Fig. 3. Exploratory data analysis of input variables as per: a) normalised mutual information matrix according to weak inter-variable dependencies, b) boxplots as per skewed and heavy-tailed distributions with multiple high-leverage observations, c) Scatter matrix based on weak linear relationships among inputs, and d) PCA score plot ($PC1 = 23.8\%$, $PC2 = 22.1\%$) as per nonlinear variance patterns coloured by RP

The scatter matrix of input variables is shown in Figure 3c, enabling a visual examination of pairwise correlations. Consistent with the low NMI values (see Fig. 3a), the scatter plots exhibit diffuse and weakly structured patterns, confirming the absence of significant linear correlations. While CT and IC histograms along the diagonal indicate heavy-tailed distributions, $Metal\ type$ and pH plots' vertical and horizontal bands are the result of their discrete or limited numeric levels. The absence of clear patterns indicates that potential correlations between these characteristics and RP are likely nonlinear and influenced by complex interactions rather than simple linear dependencies.

The first two Principal Components ($PC1$ and $PC2$) account for 23.8% and 22.1% of the total variance, respectively, according to the PCA score plot displayed in Figure 3d. Together, $PC1$ and $PC2$ explain about 45.9% of the total variance, indicating that nearly half of the dataset variability is represented in the two-dimensional PCA space, while the

remaining variance is distributed across higher components. This further confirms the inherent complexity of the adsorption dataset. The combination of discrete (Metal type, pH) and continuous (*MA*, *CT*, *IC*) variables results in a cross-shaped pattern in the score distribution. It is implied that *RP* variation results from a number of interrelated elements rather than a dominant linear trend because the *RP* colour gradient does not correspond linearly with either component.

In general, Figure 3 shows that the dataset is statistically complete, with skewed and heavy-tailed distributions and low correlation among predictors. The nonlinear structure indicates that advanced methods such as *ML* and *GA* or their integrations are suitable for predicting *RP* and supporting automated optimisation of the adsorption process.

In accordance with Zhao et al. [36], who highlighted that heavy metal adsorption systems display multivariate yet weakly coupled nonlinearities prior to interaction effects predominating, enabling *ML* models to isolate governing parameters, the weak mutual information among input variables suggests minimal collinearity. Therefore, under these conditions, the application of *ML* models is essential for addressing this type of problem, as adopted in this study.

Figure 4 presents the *ANN-GA* results, covering model diagnostics, optimisation outcomes, and prediction performance. With dispersion only rising at the highest removal levels, Figure 4a demonstrates a close parity between actual and predicted *RP* for all three metals ($R^2 = 0.908$, $RMSE = 7.43\%$, $MAE = 5.04\%$). As shown in Figure 4g, rapid error reduction occurs within approximately 5-8 epochs, and the stable test curve indicates minimal overfitting and good generalisation. Consistent with the heavy-tailed inputs previously noted, the residuals in Figure 4h exhibit a small mean bias (mean = 0.49), approximately homoscedastic variance, and are largely limited within $\pm 2\sigma$ ($\sigma = 7.47$), with a few pronounced deviations observed at high *RP* values ($> 50\%$).

Fig. 4. *ANN-GA* outcomes for ion removal based on: a) actual vs. predicted *RP* values, b) *GA* settings and optimal value suggestions for all input parameters (pH, *MA*, *CT*, and *IC*), c) maximum performance of *RP* per ion, d) cost function values per ion, e) convergence to best cost by 50 generations, f) sensitivity analysis of input variables, g) learning curves as per stable generalisation, h) residuals values, and i) Pearson correlation matrix of input/output parameters

The GA optimisation is reported in Figures 4b-e. Over 50 generations, the GA gradually reduces the best objective function (for instance, Pb^{2+} : Fig. 4e), keeping the best and mean costs apart and preventing protracted stalls, which shows ongoing exploitation with some population variety. In Figure 4b, high pH (near the top bound), $MA \approx (8.26-10)$ g/L, specific $IC \approx (46.2-86.2)$ mg/L, and metal-specific CT (high for Pb^{2+}/Co^{2+} and lower for Mn^{2+}) are the clustered optimal operating points. As shown in Figures 4c and 4d, Mn^{2+} reaches a maximum removal of 71.6 % and exhibits the highest optimisation cost function value (805.19), compared with Pb^{2+} , which achieves 100 % removal with zero cost, and Co^{2+} , which attains 87.8 % removal with a cost of 148.89.

These results indicate that Mn^{2+} requires process intensification or an expanded design space, as it is inherently more difficult to remove under the studied conditions. The results of the optimisation for critical parameters vs. RP are demonstrated in Table 1.

Table 1

The results of ANN-GA model optimisation based on experimental input data

Metal ion	IC [mg/L]	pH [-]	MA [g/L]	CT [min]	RP [%]
Pb^{2+}	46.2	4.8	8.26	109	100
Co^{2+}	86.2	5	9.99	120	87.8
Mn^{2+}	82.9	5	10	73	71.62

The interpretation of the model results in Figures 4f and 4i is the same. According to the normalised sensitivity analysis, metal type emerges as the dominant control variable (1.000), followed by pH (0.528) with a strong secondary influence, while MA (0.018), CT (≈ 0), and IC (0.004) exhibit very limited direct sensitivity. Moreover, Figure 4i presents the Pearson correlation matrix, showing the relationships between RP and the other heavy metal adsorption variables. Most notably, RP exhibits a strong negative correlation with metal type (-0.63), indicating that as the metal type defined number increases (from Pb^{2+} to Mn^{2+}), RP values tend to decrease substantially. Conversely, RP demonstrates a moderate positive correlation with pH (0.54), suggesting that higher pH levels are associated with elevated RP values. Additionally, RP shows a weak to moderate positive relationship with MA (0.32), while CT displays only a minimal correlation (0.18). The IC parameter appears nearly independent of RP , with a correlation coefficient of -0.02 . Together, these diagnostics are used to support the ANN as a reliable surrogate model for GA-based search, and a practical strategy is suggested in which pH control is prioritised, MA is adjusted as a secondary lever, and CT and IC are treated as lower-order constraints.

The ANN-GA hybrid approach has demonstrated strong predictive capabilities across various adsorption systems. Fan et al. [37] achieved $R^2 = 0.99$ for Cd^{2+} removal using Reduced Graphene Oxide-Supported Nanoscale Zero-Valent Iron (nZVI/rGO) composites, while Halder et al. [38] reported $R^2 = 0.991$ for Cr^{6+} adsorption optimisation, and Mandal et al. [39] obtained $R^2 = 0.975$ for As^{3+} removal. The current study's $R^2 = 0.908$, while slightly lower, is attributable to the inherent variability of waste-derived adsorbents (LDC) compared to engineered materials, and single-metal batch experiments. Importantly, the current study extends beyond prediction accuracy to integrate GA optimisation and MC uncertainty quantification, providing operational robustness metrics (CV values) absent in prior ANN-only approaches. The identification of pH as dominant variable aligns with Mandal et al. [39] findings, confirming the reliability of the sensitivity analysis despite the moderate R^2 value.

GA convergence across metals is compared in Figure 5a-c. For Pb^{2+} (Fig. 5a), the best-cost value decreases rapidly from $\sim 10^{-4}$ to less than 10^{-6} ($\approx 99.3\%$ reduction in the cost function relative to the initial GA baseline) with a reduction of best-mean gap. Moreover, for Co^{2+} (Fig. 5b), the best-cost decreases nearly exponentially from \sim more than $2 \cdot 10^3$ to 148.89 ($\approx 94.3\%$ improvement), indicating the stable convergence. Finally, for Mn^{2+} (Fig. 5c), the best cost remains high (805.19) despite a 47.5% improvement, indicating a more difficult optimisation landscape.

Fig. 5. GA convergence by metal: a) Pb^{2+} , b) Co^{2+} and c) Mn^{2+} . GA conditions: population size: 100, 50 generations, elite count: 10, crossover fraction: 0.80, fitness based on squared deviation of removal percentage from 100 %

Fig. 6. Response surfaces (RP vs. pH, MA): a) Pb^{2+} (CT: 109 min, IC: 46.2 mg/L) and b) Co^{2+} (CT: 120 min, IC: 86.2 mg/L), and c) Mn^{2+} (CT: 73 min, IC: 82.9 mg/L) as per ANN-GA simulations, GA conditions: population size: 100, 50 generations, elite count: 10, crossover fraction: 0.80, fitness based on squared deviation of removal percentage from 100 %

For each Metal type at different specific CT and IC, Figure 6 plots the ANN-GA response surfaces of RP against pH and MA. As MA approaches approximately (6.67-10) g/L, RP increases markedly, with improvements near the lower acidity boundary ($\text{pH} \approx 5$) further enhanced by pH effects. At high MA and pH, Pb^{2+} shows near-complete removal across a broad region (Fig. 6a). Moreover, Co^{2+} exhibits a similar trend but with different pH-MA interaction effects (Fig. 6b). Besides, Mn^{2+} displays a smoother response and a lower removal plateau of about 70% (Fig. 6c), indicating lower adsorption efficiency. Pb^{2+} has a lower hydration energy and acts as a softer Lewis acid, which favors strong inner-sphere complexation with alkaline LDC surface sites and permits incipient precipitation as $\text{Pb}(\text{OH})_2$ /basic carbonates at high pH [25]. This superiority is mechanistically feasible. These findings align with those of Macena et al. [40], who

determined that variations in adsorption affinity among heavy metals are affected mainly by ionic softness, hydration state, and the extent of complexation with surface functional groups.

The ANN-GA framework's model-based outputs for single factors vs. *RP*, are shown in Figures 7a-d. The effects of pH, *MA*, *CT*, and *IC* on *RP* collectively reveal a consistent adsorption hierarchy among the metal ions. Increasing pH enhances *RP* for Pb^{2+} and Co^{2+} , leading to high removal efficiencies at the upper pH range, whereas Mn^{2+} exhibits a weaker and more gradual response, with moderate removal efficiency at higher pH. In parallel, increasing *MA* strongly promotes *RP* for all metals, with Pb^{2+} and Co^{2+} showing a sharp rise, while Mn^{2+} requires higher *MA* values to achieve comparable performance. Prolonged *CT* has a limited additional effect, rapidly driving Pb^{2+} and Co^{2+} toward early saturation, whereas Mn^{2+} remains partially kinetically constrained. Conversely, increasing *IC* reduces *RP* due to active site saturation, with this inhibitory effect being most pronounced for Mn^{2+} because of its weaker surface affinity. From the standpoint of control systems, the main variables that should be changed (high loop gain) are pH and *MA*. Then, *CT* should be adjusted for each metal (longer for Co^{2+}). The outcomes illustrated in Figure 7d indicate that *IC* has the lowest influence on *RP* according to the ANN-GA model, exhibits an inverse relationship with *RP*, and, due to its fluctuations, should be specifically controlled for Co^{2+} at the optimal values reported in Table 1.

Fig. 7. ANN-GA response curves for Pb^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Mn^{2+} as per: a) pH vs. *RP*, b) *MA* vs. *RP*; c) *CT* vs. *RP*; d) *IC* vs. *RP*, GA conditions: population size: 100, 50 generations, elite count: 10, crossover fraction: 0.80, fitness based on squared deviation of removal percentage from 100 %. Note: In each plot, the remaining factors are fixed at their optimal values as listed in Table 1

Huang et al. [41] explained that precipitation, surface complexation, and ion exchange within the C–S–H and ettringite phases are necessary for heavy metal stabilisation in waste-based matrices, and the GA optimisation results following ANN prediction in this study are in good agreement with their findings. Co^{2+} and Mn^{2+} showed lesser fixation because they were present in more soluble forms, such as $\text{MnSO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, but Pb^{2+} demonstrated the highest stability through the development of insoluble hydroxide and phosphate precipitates ($\text{Pb}(\text{OH})_2$, $\text{Pb}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2$). Stronger adsorption and precipitation under alkaline conditions are confirmed by the observed pH-dependent enhancement in removal, which is in line with Huang's [41] solidification mechanisms.

Figure 8 quantifies the reliability of the optimal operating rules under input variability and complements the preceding ANN-GA results. MC uncertainty analysis of the ANN-GA model is reported in all panels.

Fig. 8. ANN-GA-MC (2,000 runs) uncertainty: a) RP distributions, b) boxplots of MC analysis, c) means with 95/99 % Confidence Intervals (CIs), d) steep CDFs indicate robustness (Pb²⁺, Co²⁺), e) CVs in the three metals adsorption onto LDC, and f) PDFs to set control margins, MC Conditions: 2000 runs, $\pm 5\%$ perturbation of pH, MA, CT, IC, ANN-based RP uncertainty

After 2000 MC cycles at GA-recommended settings (Fig. 8a), uncertainty quantification reveals metal-specific variability patterns. By absolute standard deviation, Pb²⁺ (SD = 2.1 %) shows the lowest variability, followed by Mn²⁺ (SD = 2.3 %) and Co²⁺ (SD = 4.5 %). In the probability density histograms, Mn²⁺ exhibits the tallest peak due to its untruncated distribution around 70 %, while Pb²⁺'s distribution near the physical 100 % limit appears broader due to edge effects, and Co²⁺ displays the widest spread centered at 84.2 %.

Boxplots of the MC-predicted RP values are shown in Figure 8b. Pb²⁺ confirms modest dispersion and consistent performance with a narrow interquartile range and few deviant values. Co²⁺ shows significant variability under uncertainty with a large interquartile range and several low-value outliers. Mn²⁺ exhibits a modest spread, much narrower than Co²⁺ but bigger than Pb²⁺, indicating regulated but not insignificant variability. Further, Figure 8c compares the MC mean RP values with their corresponding 95 % CI. Pb²⁺ achieves a mean RP of 99.6 %, with a 95 % CI of [94.51 %, 102.31 %], confirming near-complete and highly reliable removal. Co²⁺ reaches a mean RP of 84.2 %, with a wider 95 % CI of [71.87 %, 87.94 %], indicating reduced robustness. Mn²⁺ exhibits a mean RP of 70.00 %, bounded by a narrower 95 % CI of [63.37 %, 71.62 %], reflecting moderate stability around its optimal value.

The CDFs of RP are shown in Figure 8d. The steep slope of the Pb²⁺ CDF indicates a high probability of achieving RP values close to the optimum with minimal uncertainty. Besides, the more gradual slope observed for Co²⁺ reflects greater variability and a higher

likelihood of deviation from ideal performance. The Mn^{2+} CDF lies between these two extremes, indicating moderate robustness and resilience. Moreover, each metal ion's CV is shown in Figure 8e. The most reliable prediction is Pb^{2+} , which shows the least fluctuation ($CV = 2.13\%$). The moderately stable system under stochastic perturbations is Mn^{2+} , which exhibits moderate variability ($CV = 3.29\%$), but Co^{2+} surpasses the 5% robustness barrier ($CV = 5.39\%$) based on the study of González-Fernández et al. [42]. The $PDFs$ of RP are shown in Figure 8f, with shaded areas denoting the 95% confidence intervals and dashed lines denoting the MC mean. Strong dependability and narrow control margins are confirmed by the crisp, high-density peak that Pb^{2+} displays. Because of its flatter and wider density profile, Co^{2+} needs more cautious operational management. Once more, Mn^{2+} exhibits intermediate behaviour, with reasonable uncertainty boundaries and a moderately concentrated density.

To assess parameter sensitivity in micellar-enhanced ultrafiltration, Lin et al.'s [43] MC - ANN model employed 1000 stochastic iterations. It achieved over 99% metal rejection and identified pH and surfactant ratio as the dominating parameters with the least amount of model uncertainty. Similarly, to evaluate resilience and regulate variability, the current ANN - GA - MC paradigm combines evolutionary optimisation with probabilistic MC simulations.

The MATLAB-based system illustrates how ML , optimisation, and sensor-based analytics are integrated under the Industry 4.0 paradigm in the simulated operation of the ES within an industrial water treatment plant. The ES turns static adsorption modelling into a dynamic decision-support environment that can intelligently govern processes, as seen in Figure 9 as the online dashboard output. The average RP for Pb^{2+} , Co^{2+} , and Mn^{2+} ions is continuously forecasted on the real-time control dashboard, which is shown in the upper panel. Across 200 synthetic test scenarios with varied operational conditions, Pb^{2+} exhibits the highest average RP (69.4%), followed by Co^{2+} (63%) and Mn^{2+} (47%), while GA -optimised conditions achieve maximum removals of 100% (Pb^{2+}), 87.8% (Co^{2+}), and 71.6% (Mn^{2+}).

The simulation's varied operational variability is validated by the pH and sorbent mass distributions obtained from 200 synthetic sensor-based test datasets. Time and concentration are secondary under optimised regimes, while pH and sorbent mass dominate process sensitivity, as seen by the ideal parameter heatmap. The capacity of the system to generalise predictions under industrial noise and uncertainty is demonstrated by the ANN training and validation curves ($R^2 = 0.993$), which show consistent convergence with little overfitting. In this study, $R^2 = 0.908$ represents the ANN performance on training, validation, and testing, while $R^2 = 0.993$ is obtained within the ES using simulated sensor-based data (just training and validation). The observed difference ($\Delta R^2 \approx 0.085$) reflects the exclusion of unseen test data and the resulting evaluation under more stable, operator-controlled conditions. This difference does not imply a change in model structure, but rather the performance of the same ANN when assessed using training and validation data only.

From a smart operational perspective, the ES integrates predictive analytics with autonomous optimisation loops. The GA iteratively refines operational setpoints to maximise the RP of Pb^{2+} , Co^{2+} , and Mn^{2+} , with ANN outputs continuously integrated into the GA -based control logic. These results indicate that the system can adaptively regulate treatment parameters, maintaining process efficiency despite fluctuating influent quality.

Fig. 9. Industrial water treatment control centre dashboard of the developed *ES* as per sensor-based data processing, *ANN-GA* predictive modelling, parameter optimisation, and intelligent monitoring within an Industry 4.0 operational framework

Figure 10 presents the online dashboard output, illustrating the optimisation outcomes of the *ES* through 3D response surface plots and contour maps for each metal ion. The surfaces visualise the nonlinear interplay between pH and MA on RP, illustrating that performance enhancement is primarily achieved within the high-pH, high-MA domain. The overlaid optimal points indicate the system's ability to autonomously discover the most efficient zones for operation.

Fig. 10. Digital twin dashboard according to *ANN-GA*-based optimisation analysis, response surfaces, and optimal operational zones for Pb^{2+} , Co^{2+} , and Mn^{2+} adsorption in industrial level analysis

Using an *ANN*, *RF*, Radial Basis Function kernel, and Adaptive Neuro-Fuzzy Inference System (*ANFIS*), Pathania et al. [44] created an online *AI*-based wastewater monitoring system that predicts pollutant adsorption in real time. However, their approach focused on prediction without optimisation. Wilson et al. [45] created a real-time biosorption monitoring system from an automation standpoint by combining an *ANN* model with an electronic tongue and a flow-injection potentiometric setup to assess transient signals from ion-selective sensors. This setup made it possible to identify several metals at once and partially automate the monitoring procedure. In order to facilitate optimisation and decision-making inside an Industry 4.0, the current study combines *ANN*, *GA*, and *MC* to advance automation.

By coupling *ANN-GA* predictive modelling with *MC*-based uncertainty analysis, the developed *ES* not only predicts and optimises removal efficiencies for Pb^{2+} , Co^{2+} , and Mn^{2+} but also quantifies operational robustness under realistic variations. The current approach changes adsorption modelling from a static optimisation or data-driven prediction tool into a decision-support system capable of real-time process control. This advancement aligns with the emerging concept of Virtual Laboratories [46], enabling digital experimentation, model validation, and process optimisation in simulated environments. Consequently, it establishes a scalable digital twin framework for sustainable water treatment systems. This could make it easier to connect with Internet of Things (*IoT*)-based sensing and real-time industrial automation in the future.

Conclusion

In this study, the *ANN-GA* framework predicted optimal removal efficiencies of 100 % for Pb^{2+} , 87.8 % for Co^{2+} , and 71.62 % for Mn^{2+} , with predictive accuracy of $R^2 = 0.908$ and $RMSE = 7.43$ %. *MC* analysis confirmed high operational robustness for Pb^{2+} ($CV = 2.13$ %) and Mn^{2+} ($CV = 3.29$ %), while Co^{2+} showed higher variability ($CV = 5.39$ %). By combining automation, uncertainty analysis, and process sustainability, the *ES* offers managerial decision assistance beyond technical optimisation, facilitating data-driven resource management and operational resilience in water treatment systems. By transforming construction and demolition waste into high-value functional adsorbents, the framework reduces reliance on virgin materials, reinforces circular resource utilisation, and contributes to UN SDGs 6 (Clean Water), 9 (Industry Innovation), and 12 (Responsible Consumption). In order to support sustainable process automation and informed policy development for environmental protection, the methodology converts static experimental insights into an eco-efficient digital twin framework. To improve sustainability, scalability, and circular economy integration in industrial water treatment, future research might expand the *ES* to dynamic multi-metal and real wastewater conditions, incorporate *IoT*-based real-time monitoring, and investigate hybrid organic waste-*LDC* composites.

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